

Maximising Sub-Saharan Africa's Impact in the Global Data for Policy Dialogue

Stakeholder Consultation Report

Published by:

Data for Policy CIC

November 2024

This document provides an overview of the inaugural strategic consultation of the **Data for Policy SSA Engagement Programme**, held on **30 March, 2023** in **Nairobi, Kenya**. The event brought together 30 regional thought leaders. It explored ways to enhance African connectivity and international contributions to the data-for-policy field, emphasising climate action and advancing data science capabilities as focal points.

Cite as: Data for Policy Sub-Saharan Africa Programme: Consultation Reports, November 2024
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14237003>

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Maximising Sub-Saharan Africa's Impact In The Global Data for Policy Dialogue

30 March 2023 | Radisson Blu Hotel Nairobi, Upper Hill, Kenya

1. Executive Summary

The Fourth Industrial Revolution is rapidly transforming the world as the digital economy impacts every facet of our lives. This sweeping change not only presents a wealth of commercial opportunities, but it also yields an array of data and information that, when employing data science to properly analyse and interpret, significantly enhances decision-making and investment within the public sector. To effectively harness these advantages, we must foster understanding, connectivity, and collaboration among data generators, researchers, policy makers, investors, and users.

Data for Policy CIC (DfP) is the non-profit organisation at the hub of a global network that operates at the interface of data science, governance, and policy, promoting interdisciplinary and cross-sector dialogue on the implications and potential of the digital revolution within the public sector. DfP provides collaborative platforms such as online forums, regional and international conferences, and the open access Data & Policy Journal that empower stakeholders to fully leverage data science, thus fostering innovation and informed decision-making.

DfP – with regional co-host the Kenya Institute for Public Policy Research and Analysis – directed the event 'Maximising Sub-Saharan Africa's impact in the Global Data for Policy Dialogue: A Strategic Consultation' held on 30 March 2023 in Nairobi, Kenya. A collaboration between Data for Policy CIC, the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation, and the Evans School of Public Policy & Governance at the University of Washington, the strategic consultation assembled 30 regional thought leaders and initiated inclusive dialogue to enhance African connectivity and international contribution in the data for policy field, with emphasis on climate action and data science capabilities as our starting point. It also enhanced collective understanding of the challenges, opportunities, visions, and direction for expediting African intracontinental and global engagement, collaboration, and impact at the intersection of data and policy for sustainable development and the betterment of the African data-policy ecosystem.

Over the course of the day, researchers, practitioners, civil society, and private sector stakeholders from Kenya, Rwanda, South Africa, and Uganda framed crucial issues, presented findings, shared expertise and lessons learned, and debated and synthesized strategies for action. Although timely issues such as agriculture, climate action and data science capabilities provided some grounding, the cross sectoral dialogue branched all aspects of the African data-policy pipeline – from knowledge generation and formulating research questions to daily use at the frontline. The dialogue included a series of engaging panel discussions on topics such as African knowledge generation and impact on the regional and global stage, impact of African-led research at the nexus of data and policy, and a collaborative theory of change. Participants discussed national, sector- and field-specific contexts, taxonomies, challenges, opportunities and key decision points influencing

Africa's data and policy landscape, and strategic areas of interest for addressing these challenges.

Additionally, DfP and its collaborators met with regional organizations and/or their representatives that exemplify crucial activities along the data-for-policy pipeline. Along with KIPPRA, organizations and programs were the Kenya National Bureau of Statistics, University of Nairobi's (UoN) Women Economic Empowerment Hub, UoN's USAID Health-IT project, the African Institute for Development Policy, and the Council of Governors.

Outcomes from the strategic dialogue and organizational meetings complement DfP's other research and outreach activities on the African data-policy ecosystem and will feed into the development of a collaborative strategy for longer term sustainability and productivity of these conversations.

2. Background

Data science and artificial intelligence offer unprecedented capacity and potential to inform policy and create more equitable and sustainable societies. However, the global knowledge base lacks critical expertise, data, and insights generated from large geographical areas. This has led to incomplete data and biased responses to global challenges such as climate change, economic shocks, and infectious disease spread. There is a need to employ appropriate interventions that ensure data science's societal impact reduces, rather than widens, existing global inequities.

African institutions are driving sustainable data science and evidence-based policy making through research, implementation, innovation, and facilitation. However, African-led spaces for knowledge creation, cross-disciplinary and cross-sector dialogue, and global dissemination of African-generated research inquiries, data, theories, practices, contributions, and solutions are limited. Africa has 650 peer-reviewed journals, spanning 37 African countries, accounting for 7.6% of scientific contributions (and one-third of publications in tropical medicine). Yet, approximately 50% come from two countries - Egypt and South Africa. New infrastructure and platforms present a historical opportunity to connect expertise from diverse disciplines, sectors, and geographies to address systemic problems and develop novel approaches for ethical, open, and inclusive research and practice.

Data for Policy CIC (DfP) is a global network that operates at the interface of data science, governance, and policy. DfP acts as an international forum for interdisciplinary and cross-sector dialogue on the impact and potential of the digital revolution within the public sector, looking to bridge the gap between research and practice of using data for policy. DfP works by:

- Amplifying methodologies and tools that connect data to policy;
- Hosting collaborative platforms such as online forums and regional and international conferences for active engagement and knowledge sharing; and
- Editing an open access Data & Policy Journal for information sharing.

Additionally, DfP empowers stakeholders to implement proactive strategies for rapid response to both dynamic and difficult problems in data science's policy and societal impact. DfP platforms are steadily attracting an expanding network of international thought leaders and practitioners focused on the intersection of data and policy. Despite being a global platform, most participation stems from Europe and North America, with a growing presence

from Asia and South America. However, representation from researchers and practitioners in Sub-Saharan Africa remains limited. As a result, the community has restricted access to the knowledge, methodologies, and practices from this region.

To address this imbalance, DfP aims to enhance the contribution and active participation of Sub-Saharan African professionals in dialogues and idea generation. Simultaneously, the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation (BMGF) seeks to promote data-driven decision-making in agricultural policies and investments while bolstering the market for data-driven policy formulation and implementation. Recognizing the potential for collaboration, BMGF has funded DfP to explore and present a business plan for targeted initiatives to increase the involvement of Sub-Saharan African researchers, academics, policymakers, technical experts, advocates, and organizations in the DfP community. Additionally, they should also increase the submission and publication of policy-data interactions by Sub-Saharan African professionals.

3. Structure

To achieve this goal, DfP carried out desk research to gather insights on regional operating and publishing ecosystems, as well as the intersection of data and policy. They conducted key informant interviews to assess the relevance and added value of their community and platform, and to gauge interest in engagement and partnerships in Sub-Saharan Africa.

A key part of this project was to organise regional strategic consultations with key stakeholders in SSA. This document reports on the first of these meetings "Maximising Sub-Saharan Africa's Impact in the Global Data for Policy Dialogue: A Strategic Consultation", held in Nairobi, Kenya, on March 30, 2023.

DfP designed the day's agenda to foster comprehensive and engaging discussions on sector-specific, cross-sector, and vertical integration of data for policy. It commenced with opening remarks and an address to set the stage, followed by panel discussions guided by prompt questions, which allowed participants to share their thoughts and feedback. These panel discussions were interspersed with breaks, facilitating networking and reflection. In the latter part of the event, plenary discussions and group work aimed at finding solutions and building consensus on key issues were held. This well-structured format ensured a dynamic and productive exchange of ideas, ultimately contributing to the development of a shared vision and actionable steps for the future. The consultation brought together thirty regional African researchers and practitioners working at the nexus of data and policy. Participants shared their expertise and experiential knowledge, provided valuable input on closing gaps in the "data to policy to impact" pipeline, and deepened their understanding of cross-sector perspectives, objectives, and priorities.

DfP believes that African methodologies and tools that effectively link data to policy are beneficial for and hold potential to make a significant impact on the global stage and is committed to offering platforms that promote and elevate their significance.

4. Insights

4.1 African knowledge generation and impact on regional and global stage

Desired states of knowledge creation, diffusion, and integration into policy and governance

There are complexities surrounding data driven and policy-making in Africa. A critical gap between research and policy, which has led to a weak link between the two domains, remains. This disconnect can be attributed to the different incentive structures and lack of capacity building along the data to policy pipeline among researchers and policy-makers alike. There is a need to understand the landscape of data requirements and usage to create effective policies. There is also the question about the purpose and intended audience for the data and insight, as well as the challenges in facilitating constructive engagement between policy-makers and data sources.

There are several strategies to improve the situation. It is essential to foster better partnerships between various stakeholders, including government, private sector, and non-state actors. By building these relationships, stakeholders can identify and address strategic areas based on experiential insight, ensure the use of all available data sources, and create a more cohesive data ecosystem. Additionally, there is a need to invest in capacity development to adopt data science approaches tailored to the local context. This would involve investing in research and development of relevant technologies and making use of existing data from various sources, such as administrative data, private sector data, and routine monitoring – whilst being cognizant of their inherent limitations.

However, it is pertinent to acknowledge that decision points – especially in policy-making – are often influenced by political considerations, which can affect the data ecosystem's development. Governments may not invest sufficiently in data generation and use, resulting in a reliance on donor funding and a skewed data landscape. To overcome this issue, there is a call for mindset change among researchers and policy-makers to better align their goals and create an environment that fosters policy-oriented research. This shift would involve prioritising the effective use of data in policy-making, engaging in collaborative efforts, and focusing on generating research that answers pressing questions relevant to the African context. By adopting these strategies, stakeholders can work towards a more integrated and impactful knowledge generation process on both regional and global stages.

Discussion

Further dialogue provided deeper insights into the data and policy landscape in Africa, including the importance of adopting an enterprising mindset, understanding policy-makers' needs, empowering individuals to share their stories, and addressing data quality and policy concerns.

Adopting an enterprising mindset calls for stakeholders to think creatively about and emphasize “value” when generating and utilizing data for both private and public sectors. By connecting data dissemination and policy prioritization, stakeholders can better ensure that data initiatives align with the most pressing policy needs and social and commercial wants. Furthermore, it is important to understand private and public sector requirements and provide tools to solve complex problems. Equally, there is power in narratives (story telling) and its ability to influence policy-making. Empowering individuals to share their stories can lead to more inclusive and effective policies. These insights on the demand-driven approach

to data generation and influence speak to the value of translational research, which seeks to bridge the gap between academic findings and real-world applications, ensuring that research is responsive to societal needs. Bias in data collection and quality, which may stem from national systems prioritising or excluding certain groups, remains a concern. This underscores the importance of addressing data quality and considering alternative institutional frameworks that may better serve the needs of policy-makers *and* researchers.

There is also room for addressing the dynamism and interoperability of African data policy, which links to the broader data ecosystem and the potential impact that data sharing, stewardship, and protection have on the availability and quality of data for policy-making. By fostering an environment that encourages and facilitates data access, stakeholders can ensure that valuable information can be and is used to inform policy decisions.

4.2 Evidenced Impact of African-led Research at the Nexus of Data and Policy

Assessing status, key players, supporting and/or countering regional and international narratives

African-led research puts special emphasis on the importance of and solving local data-related challenges. Although support is largely external, there are other regional and national support systems including universities, national and county level offices, and regional civil society organizations and think tanks. Of course, these could be better financed. African researchers and practitioners have limited “freedom to fail” – as submissions, proposals, etc. face tougher scrutiny. This constraint often impacts the type of research being funded and conducted in Africa. Consequently, there are concerns about the legitimacy of unofficial statistics. Thus, it is important to bridge the gap between these data sources and official statistics.

There is a need for a dual approach – incorporating both rapid revolutionary changes and deliberate, slower adjustments – to ensure that when the context is right, data science benefits can effectively and rapidly be exploited. The importance of leveraging the youth dividend and guiding young people towards effective data science skills, particularly around data generation, and usage cannot be understated. Increased research and development funding from the continent, particularly through the private sector and NGOs, is a critical factor in addressing the challenges faced by academia trying to meet these needs.

Resources and capacity building to understand the importance of linking evidence to policy and for implementation extends beyond the universities. Sustainable capacity-building – along with strong government leadership – is needed in public sector data generation and contributions to the evidence-to-policy pipeline. Most importantly, the public sector is in the most advantageous position to address biases within official statistics and its application in policy making, investment, and expenditures.

Discussion

Further discussions touched on breaking down barriers, not only between official and unofficial data sources, but also between anglophone and francophone countries. As they work from different post-colonial frameworks, there is a need to invest in research on closing barriers of communication and collaboration and general capacity gaps within Africa. Such gaps may (and already have) lead to power dynamics where certain countries become suppliers (and potential gatekeepers) of crucial data sets. However, this may be a challenge as African governments tend to thrive on opacity, even when working with institutions from within their countries. It is essential that advocacy around open governance is continually supported.

So how can data for policy proponents package data for communication and influence with policymakers? The private sector may be an important partner in research and advocacy. Apprehensions may arise as a select few private sector entities will dominate research inquiries, particularly given that most African private sector organizations consist of micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises with limited capacity and influence. Nonetheless, it is essential to acknowledge the private sector's current role in attracting top talent, financing fundamental research, and shaping messaging, discourse, and sentiment in various contexts. It may be pertinent, where there is shared value, to partner with the private sector to advance interest in and demand for data for policy.

4.3 Data & Policy Journal – Impact at the Nexus of Data and Policy

The Data & Policy Journal offers valuable opportunities for stakeholders to explore avenues for fostering sub-Saharan African involvement in the global data and policy environment. A peer-reviewed publication affiliated with Cambridge University Press, the journal is committed to disseminating data-for-policy research and translational work through an open-access model, ensuring its availability to a wide-ranging audience.

The Data & Policy Journal aspires to enhance comprehension of the data-for-policy environment in sub-Saharan Africa, address potential obstacles or dissatisfaction concerning publishing, and actively engage new authors, reviewers, and editors from and working within the region. Moreover, the journal seeks to share insights from sub-Saharan Africa with its global readership. With engagement from authors across 70 countries and a team of 47 editors from different nations, the journal has cultivated an integrated conference-to-journal process, encompassing rigorous peer review and expedited publication.

Emphasizing data transparency, the journal asks for Data Availability Statements, supports Annotation for Transparent Inquiry, and publishes in-line code and computational notebooks. The journal is also at the forefront of implementing workflows for pre-registration and registered reports, while also experimenting with open peer review models. The Data & Policy Journal publishes an array of content, including research articles, translational articles emphasizing practical lessons, commentaries, and data descriptors that advocate data reuse. The journal is one of the many ways research information is disseminated. The Data & Policy blog provides a platform for immediate perspectives and summary research for a more extensive audience, encompassing academic researchers, government representatives, non-profits, and international organizations.

The journal is presently spearheading forthcoming collections that tackle pertinent topics on African cities, peace initiatives, and citizen-generated data in October 2023. To amplify engagement of African scholars and practitioners, the journal seeks recommendations for potential Editorial Committee members, and research publication submissions. Additionally, the journal welcomes assistance in addressing pressing questions regarding the data-for-policy landscape in sub-Saharan Africa, especially on promoting an open publishing culture and mitigating frustrations within publishing processes.

The journal's dedication to multi- and transdisciplinary research, diverse portfolio of publishable article types, adherence to open access, unambiguous templates, and equitable submission and support policies, and investment in sub-Saharan African scholarly contributions demonstrates tangible, action-based ways to support the sub-Saharan data for policy pipeline.

4.4 A Collaborative Theory of Change

Strategic areas of interest that can address challenges

The potential for a common vision and strategy to tackle data for policy challenges and its implementation across various sectors exist. African governments are seemingly converging on the importance of domestic evidence-based policymaking to tackle internally identified development challenges which may include poverty reduction, nutrition, and social inequalities. There was consensus on the importance of interdisciplinary approaches; the need to bring together diverse stakeholders with distinctive needs, views, priorities, and incentives; as well as the crucial role of the private sector and business in realizing a common vision. Business schools were also identified as potential ecosystems where stakeholders can aggregate, share their vision, and direct activities. However, it is paramount that any vision has the support of strong leadership and influential advocacy and includes data sovereignty in conjunction with regional coherence in data policy for meaningful cross-border data sharing. Therefore, researchers and practitioners must invest time in advocating for an enabling environment and legal frameworks to support the usage of data, capacity building for government personnel, and sustainable financing for data-related initiatives.

Additionally, a common vision on data policy, particularly in publishing, was recognized. However, there continues to be a lack of institutional will, support, and funding for strong Africa publishing ecosystems – from idea generation and sharing to citation and reuse. There remains a strong need and pull for spaces for research co-creation and collaboration, including incentives for data sharing, directories of data producers, and data repositories. A good example of a platform is the arXiv, an open-access repository for preprints where researchers can find the latest science, technology, and mathematics research, receive feedback from peers, and collaborate on projects before submitting their papers to academic journals. A similar platform can be established in collaboration with the African Open Science Platform. It is also important not to forget cross-cutting access such as social justice and inclusion through data science education.

To solidify a shared vision and support resulting objectives, there is a need for a multi-disciplinary approach and critical thinking about the data collected, its market, as well as the importance of communication and storytelling for persuasion in policy making. This may mean involving customers of the data (e.g., policy makers) from the beginning with hands-on implementation of projects to address data collection, integration, and sustainability in government capacity. A programme that touches upon this subject is the Open Governance Partnership which has two primary pillars of increasing transparency and access to information and leveraging technology, data, and innovation to increase transparency and improve public services.

Stakeholder engagement, cross-disciplinary platforms, and reporting and knowledge sharing are essential to progress. However, investment – whether with political, social, or financial capital – is a must. Yet funding tends to follow a pattern: governments have limited official revenue and focus on delivering essential public services and infrastructure, private sector's focus may not align with evidence-driven initiatives, and donor financing is (beyond rhetoric) still structured exogenous to government needs and desires. There are alignments. For example, support and drive for climate-related data is now high but barriers persist when collecting data for other purposes. It is important to regionally leverage data infrastructure and systems. For example, there could be an intra-governmental data sharing and prioritization, that follows the African Union's data and innovation objectives outlined in its Data Policy Framework.

Discussion

The dialogue emphasized the crucial role of the private sector in tackling public sector issues, as well as the complex challenges policymakers face in balancing election cycles, constituents' expectations, and evidence-based decision-making. Furthermore, the conversation addressed the necessity for policymakers to effectively communicate their data requirements. Working within regional blocks and the African Union presents its own set of challenges. The African Union is a particularly difficult group for researchers and practitioners to collaborate with, as engagement is typically limited to the initial stages of policy- and decision-making and follows a highly regimented structure. A significant portion of investments from the African Union is directed towards regional blocks rather than individual member states. While this approach has the potential to promote interoperability and harmonization of data policies across nations, it may inadvertently lead to the neglect of specific national priorities.

The consequences of inaction in sub-Saharan Africa are growing exponentially. As the global data science landscape continues to evolve, there is an inherent risk of the region being left behind, becoming a mere consumer of solutions rather than an active participant in their design and generation. Therefore, it is vital to address the escalating political and economic costs of ineffective policies, as well as the increasing demand for evidence-based policymaking, targeted investments, formalized feedback mechanisms, and demonstrable pipelines for data-informed policy development.

The Data for Policy (DfP) community and the Data & Policy Journal can play crucial roles in fostering this transformation by providing a platform for collaboration, knowledge sharing, and the promotion of evidence-based practices that will ultimately empower sub-Saharan Africa to significantly participate in domestic and global data science and policy arenas. Identified focus areas such as interdisciplinary collaboration, knowledge sharing across sectors, stakeholder engagement, and capacity building are components DfP can actively service. Other topics such as data sovereignty, regional coherence in data policy, and an enabling environment and legal frameworks for data usage, are also focus points that fall within DfP pillars. There is urgency to address these challenges to prevent an increase in inequality and the perpetuation of biased and partial data in decision-making processes and DfP can be part of the solution.

5. Proposals for Transformation

The dialogue produced several proposals for transforming the sub-Saharan African data for policy and investment landscape.

Item	Results
Collective Action for Change in 10 Years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Acknowledge power dynamics – including concepts of decolonization - and work towards equity · Capacity building through support for working meetings, engagements, and publications; and data stewardship training, protection, and publishing · Culture change that eliminates data silos and research duplication and promotes data quality, which may require mind-shifting activities, building from tested international frameworks such as FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable) · Strategizing on demand side, supply side, legal and regulatory frameworks, and quality; should result in a strategy framework with a robust business model
Practical Steps (Next 5 years)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Addressing data literacy gaps (researcher and practitioner) · Co-create with policy makers data generation/collection and research; and “data for policy” policies and guidelines · Co-funding resource mobilizers and technician · Creation of a fellowship for knowledge exchange, learning, and leadership to foster coordination and collaboration · Data communication and messaging strategies (visualizations, contextual data analysis) · Data sharing framework · Development of data governance and ethics sphere to guard against power disparities · Establishment of common infrastructure (repositories, observatories, sector specific dashboards, etc.) · Identify next generation data needs · Infrastructure address data literacy, skills, and data journalism · Investment in data infrastructure and use (budgetary allocations for existing structures and institutions) · Leveraging/establishing similar for a to Sustainable Development Goals (multi-stakeholder dialogue approach) · Mechanism for circling back to policy makers, reviewing what has been implemented and benchmarking · Multi-stakeholder (and transdisciplinary) approaches · Operationalize community of practice / alliance for data & policy · Promotion of data as a public asset (Open Governance Partnership), including concepts of inclusive data, citizen data, and crowdsourced data

<p>Characteristics of Success</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Data literacy present in secondary and post-secondary education · Data needs to be not just public but reliable and accessible with seals of approval that exist for repositories for example; guarantors of such seals could be at regional level (e.g., African Union) - and in community of practice by data professionals · Demonstrable pipeline (evidence of evidence on use and impact of data for policy) · Enhanced capacity – number of trained experts and policy makers · Federated infrastructure to make data available for data – health, agriculture · Greater data availability and access (FAIR principles) · Greater government investment · Increased use of data in policy-making, embedded approaches using data in agencies · More data policies adopted at the country-level · Policy for interoperability (standardization, linked data) nationality and cross-border in different sectors: agriculture, health etc. · Streamlined pipelines for recognizing, vetting, and incorporating alternative (non-official) data sources into policy making · Systematic impact evaluation <i>ex post</i> (“shadow policy watch”) · Templates for incorporating data into policy making and frameworks for outcome evaluation
<p>Essential Components for Realized and Sustainable Change</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Co-create and co-design with government, from conceptualisation to implementation) · Data collection, collaboration, coordination, and communication infrastructure · Efficient and effective resource allocation and use (value for money) · Identification of incentives (political economy / analysis) · Learn how to translate research for practice · Legal and regulatory frameworks · Partnerships - stakeholder mapping of data value-model which includes data producers, subject area experts (data, legal and ethics, sector, social science), users, and advocates (research institutions, think-tanks, funders, universities, local communities, civil society organizations and relevant data advocacy groups such as DSI Africa, Okoa Uchumi, Africa Check, Zizi Afrique, Ushahidi; regional data initiatives such as the Open Data Science Platform, media, private sector, publishers, and development partners) · Political commitment / policy makers (including Ministry of Finance (budget allocation, treasury) · Resources from public and private funding

6. Future Actions

Various themes and action steps for enhancing the data for policy pipeline in sub-Saharan Africa emerged. Most importantly, the dialogue recognized the integral role of Data for Policy in establishing a shared vision, direction, and actions that drive change. Here are the insights and recommendations to guide future roles and actions.

The importance of coordination and collaboration cannot be overstated. There is a need to leverage existing platforms and foster meaningful partnerships without reinventing the wheel. A multi-stakeholder approach involving both government and private sector and adoption of transdisciplinary perspectives would aid in addressing the complexities of issues facing Africa more effectively.

Additionally, **investment in data infrastructure is crucial to improve accessibility for researchers and policymakers; and building data literacy and analytical capacity within both government and research is necessary to increase the uptake of evidence-based policymaking.** For sustainable change, continuous, and responsive support for capacity building and professionalization is necessary. This includes translating research into accessible languages and generating translational research that meet various information needs of stakeholders. There is also a need to address the *different* literacies required for data management versus research data management. This also links to data governance and ethics which must be addressed to ensure that power dynamics are (re) balanced and data sovereignty is respected at both national and regional levels. This understanding coupled with decolonization principles and practices are key to preventing the widening of the digital divide between Africa and the West.

Ultimately, **policy makers must demonstrate political will to support and invest in data initiatives.** This includes developing robust legal and regulatory frameworks that promote data sharing and public benefit philosophies. Frameworks should support the FAIR data principles (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable), as well as the adoption of data policies and data trustworthiness endorsements from reliable sources. Building a community around data for policy, engaging with national statistics offices, “unofficial” data generators, and citizens affected by policies to incorporate diverse perspectives and foster civic participation should also be part of any investment.

The dialogue offered the following recommendations for establishing a community around data for policy and maintaining a continued discussion on the way forward.

Item	Description
Takeaways & Essential Actions	
Establish guidelines and best practices	Develop guidelines for data collection and utilization, fostering interoperability and common platforms, informing supply side
Conduct market research	Identify users' varying data, insight, and information needs depending on context, informing demand side
Investigate private sector role	Explore role of private sector in data-for-policy pipeline, as valuable resource for funding and data sourcing
Set agenda	Set agenda for data-driven policy development
Cultivate community	Establish consensus among stakeholders and establish path forward
Maintain ongoing dialogue	Facilitate progress through continuous communication
Engage Data for Policy CIC and Data & Policy Journal	Encourage to develop unified strategy with participants
Initiate catalytic actions	Forge strategic partnerships and establish sustainable structures for future growth
Involve affected citizens	Include those most affected by policies in development process and policy pipeline
Stakeholders to Engage	
Data for Policy CIC and Data & Policy Journal	Collaborate strategic guidance and support
Dialogue Participants	Work with fellow participants to drive change
Government officials	Engage officials who can influence policy related to shared priorities
National statistics offices	Collaborate with these offices to leverage data for policy development
Other national data generators	Partner with additional data sources to enhance the data-for-policy pipeline
Affected citizens	Involve citizens to inform the purpose and direction of policy
Timeline Considerations	
Account for stakeholder timelines	Consider timelines of various stakeholders ("client" timelines)
sustainability	Ensure execution of initiatives and strategies prioritizes long-term sustainability

7. Annex

Strategic Consultation Agenda

Thursday, 30 March 2023, Mt Kenya 1, Radisson Blu Hotel Nairobi, Upper Hill

Participant Arrivals

08:30 Coffee/Tea

09:00 **Welcome Remarks**

Eldah Onsomu, PhD

Director, Economic Management | Kenya Institute for Public Policy Research and Analysis

Joshua Ariga, PhD

Senior Program Officer | Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation

09:10 **Opening Address**

Data for Policy CIC, Data & Policy Journal, and Today's Objectives: Advancing discoveries, identifying gaps, and fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing in data-driven policy making

Zeynep Engin, PhD

Founding Director | Data for Policy CIC

Editor in Chief | Data & Policy, Cambridge University Press

Urgency for nexus approach to climate, agriculture, and technology systems and data for policy coordination for sustainable development

Aggie Asiimwe Konde

Vice President, Program Innovation & Delivery | AGRA

Team Q&A - Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation, Data for Policy CIC, Data & Policy Journal, and Evans School Policy Analysis and Research Group

9:30 **African knowledge generation and impact on regional and global stage**

Desired states of knowledge creation, diffusion, and integration into policy and governance

- Why are we not in desired states? (Gap analysis)
- How do you reach desired states? (Consider adaptation, innovation, or other methods given size, challenges, and era)
- What are key "decision points" that most influence Africa data and policy in your area of work or expertise?

Andrew Kizito Muganga, PhD

Chair, Department of Statistical Methods and Actuarial Science | Makerere University

Lilian Kirimi, PhD

Senior Research Fellow | Tegemeo Institute of Agricultural Policy & Development

Benjamin Avusewva

Director, Statistical Coordination and Methods | Kenya National Bureau of Statistics

Sarah N. Ssewanyana, PhD (Virtual)

Executive Director | Economic Policy Research Centre

Panel Chair

Joshua Ariga, PhD

Senior Program Officer | Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation

10:30 Coffee / Tea

11:00 **Evidenced Impact of African-led Research at the Nexus of Data and Policy**
Assessing status, key players, supporting and/or countering regional and international narratives

- What are the most promising and challenging issues within your field?
- How are your academic systems addressing these issues (if at all)?
- What are key "decision points" that, you believe, will be of most influence?

Nalishebo Meebelo, PhD (Virtual)

Executive Director | ReNAPRI

Rose Oronje, PhD (Virtual)

Director of Public Policy and Knowledge Translation, and Head of Kenya Office | African Institute for Development Policy

Siziwe Ngcwabe

Director and Co-Chair | African Evidence Network

Vukosi Marivate, PhD

ABSA UP Chair of Data Science | University of Pretoria

Chief Technology Officer | Lelapa AI

Co-Founder | Deep Learning Indaba and Maskhane NLP

Panel Chair

Stanley Wood, PhD

Senior Program Officer | Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation

Affiliate Professor, Evans School of Public Policy and Governance | University of Washington

12:00 Lunch

13:00 **Recap / Setting the Stage**
Summary findings from morning sessions
Delivering a model for change

Sarah N. Ssewanyana, PhD

Executive Director | Economic Policy Research Centre

13:05 **Data & Policy Journal**
Change in Action

Andrew Hyde (Virtual)

Publisher, Academic Journals (Data Science) | Cambridge University Press

13:15 **A Collaborative Theory of Change**
Strategic areas of interest that can address challenges

- Is there an emerging common vision and/or strategy?
- What are the spaces and places for co-creation and collective action?
- How can we collaborate to identify, plan, and implement actions?

Daisy Selematsela, PhD (Virtual)

Chair | CoDATA South Africa

Leonida Mutuku

Chair | Local Development Research Institute

Momar Dieng, PhD

Dean | African Leadership University, School of Business

Mouhamadou Bamba Sylla, PhD (Virtual)

AIMS-Canada Research Chair in Climate Change Science | African Institute of Mathematical Sciences

Rachel Adams, PhD

Principal Researcher | Research ICT Africa

Panel Chair

Zeynep Engin, PhD

Founding Director | Data for Policy CIC

14:15 *Editor in Chief | Data & Policy, Cambridge University Press*
Coffee / Tea

14:30 **Activity-based Delivery Model for Change**

Coordinated and effective actions

- What are the collective actions that can achieve our vision and/or strategy for the next 10 years and beyond?
- What are practical steps we can take in the next 5 years?
- What does success look like (i.e., performance indicators)?
- Who needs to be involved to realise that success?
- What is needed to make sure change occurs and is sustainable (e.g., capacity, structure, resources, etc.)

Panel Opening Remarks

Joy Kiru, PhD

Senior Lecturer, School of Economics | University of Nairobi

After, table discussions will be led by the following discussion chairs and rapporteurs:

Joseph Muliaro Wafula, PhD

Chair of National Committee | Co-DATA Kenya

Ahmed Amdihun, PhD

Regional Programme Manager - Easter Africa | IGAD Climate Prediction and Applications

Centre

Nara Monkam, PhD (Virtual)

Associate Professor for Economics | University of Pretoria

Rosemary Koech-Kimwato

Data Protection Officer | KCB Bank Group

Uzma Alam, PhD (Virtual)

Global Health and Data Science | Science for Africa Foundation

15:45 Plenary Discussion: **Summary and Action for Progress**

What are our items for immediate action?

Discussion Opening Remarks

Rose Ngugi, PhD

Executive Director | Kenya Institute for Public Policy Research and Analysis

Plenary Facilitator

Maureen Adoyo, PhD

Senior Researcher and Lecturer | Rongo University

16:30 **Closing**

Joshua Ariga, PhD

Senior Program Officer | Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation

Zeynep Engin, PhD

Founding Director | Data for Policy CIC

Editor in Chief | Data & Policy, Cambridge University Press

19:00 Dinner

Event Facilitator

Diasmer Panna Bloe

Researcher | Data for Policy CIC

Virtual Facilitators

Peter Agamile

Post-Doctoral Scholar, Evans School of Public Policy and Governance | University of

Washington

Wendy Essuman

Technical Project Manager | SpidiPay

8. Partners

Partners' Profiles

The Kenya Institute for Public Policy Research and Analysis (KIPPRA)

The Kenya Institute for Public Policy Research and Analysis (KIPPRA) is a public institution established in May 1997 through a Legal Notice and began its operations in June 1999. As a state corporation created by an Act of Parliament, KIPPRA's primary mandate is to provide high-quality policy advice to the Government of Kenya and other stakeholders. This is achieved through policy research, analysis, and capacity building, all aimed at contributing to the achievement of Kenya's long-term national development objectives. Headquartered in Nairobi, KIPPRA's mission is to support the realization of national development goals by offering objective policy research, conducting comprehensive policy analysis, and delivering effective capacity-building initiatives to inform and guide public policy in Kenya.

Website: <https://kippra.or.ke/>

X: @KIPPRAKENYA

Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation

The [Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation](#), based in Seattle, USA, is one of the largest charitable foundations in the world. It works to give all people the chance of a healthy, productive life. For developing countries, the focus is on health improvement and relief from hunger and poverty, whilst in the USA it strives to improve high school and post-secondary education, and economic mobility and opportunity.

Funding is directed to innovative ideas with the potential to remove barriers, with the foundation believing that the essential role of philanthropy is to back promising solutions which are unaffordable to government and business. Grants are awarded to organisations to achieve measurable impact in the fight against poverty, disease, and inequity around the world; these account for over 90% of funds given. Strategic investments are made with entrepreneurs, companies, and other organisations to create incentives that harness the power of private enterprise to create change for those who need it most.

The foundation funds work in 144 countries, and has offices worldwide, including in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia; Abuja, Nigeria and Johannesburg, South Africa.

Cambridge University Press

Founded in 1534, Cambridge University Press ([CUP](#)) is the oldest university press in the world. Today, CUP is a global organisation, publishing academic-level research, reference and higher education textbooks across a wide range of disciplines. Its online repository Cambridge Core hosts 1.6 million journal articles and 46,000 e-books, granting academics access to high-quality, digitally interconnected materials that enhance understanding and the global impact of research. CUP currently publishes more than 380 peer-reviewed academic journals, as well as thousands of books for research and education. CUP has offices and publishing hubs in more than 40 countries, with CUP Africa based in Cape Town, South Africa.

Evans School of Policy Analysis & Research Group, Evans School of Public Policy & Governance, University of Washington

The Evans School Policy Analysis & Research Group ([EPAR](#)) at the University of Washington's Daniel J. Evans School of Public Policy & Governance provides rigorous, applied research and analysis to international development stakeholders. Thematically, EPAR focusses on inclusive agricultural transformation, development policy, financial services, poverty reduction, gender, and measurement and evaluation. Most of our work is centred on countries within sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia, and much of our time is devoted to increasing the utility of data from these geographies. From the World Bank LSMS-ISA household surveys we are growing a publicly available searchable database of over 100 common agricultural statistics for Nigeria and Ethiopia ([AgQuery](#)) and a [GitHub](#) repository of code that also includes Tanzania, Malawi, and Uganda. We plan to add climate data, more countries, and an adaptation focus as we launch the University of Washington's new Center on Risk and Inclusion in Food Systems.

Organisations represented

Research ICT Africa

Rongo University, Kenya

University of Washington

Science for Africa Foundation

IGAD-Climate Protection and Application Centre

Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation

Kenya National Bureau of Statistics

The World Bank

Data for Policy CIC

African Leadership University, School of Business

SpidiPay

Cambridge University Press

University of Nairobi

Egerton University

KCB Bank Group

AGRA

(Multiple affiliations) University of Pretoria, Lelapa AI, Co-Founder, Deep Learning Indaba and Maskhane NLP

The National Research Foundation of South Africa

ReNAPRI

University of Pretoria

African Economic Research Consortium

Makerere University

Science for Africa Foundation

Strathmore University

Local Development Research Institute

African Evidence Network

Kenya Institute for Public Policy Research and Analysis
National Drought Management Authority
Tegemeo Institute
Kenya Institute for Public Policy Research and Analysis
Kenya Office, African Institute for Development Policy
IGAD Climate Prediction and Applications Centre
CoDATA South Africa
Economic Policy Research Centre
African Institute of Mathematical Sciences
Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology

Thank You

Contact Information

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 www.dataforpolicy.org